

A Study on Suicide

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Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

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**Author'(s) Name Surname: Associate Prof. Halise
Heves Özyılmaz**

(ORCID-0000-0001-6035-6031)

University: Northwest University

Department: Clinical Psychology

Date: 27. October. October.2023

Abstract

The phenomenon of suicide is a complex and varied occurrence that exhibits complicated connections to many mental, social, and cognitive factors, alongside adverse life occurrences. Given the established fact that suicide accounts for 1.4 percent

of global mortality, it is imperative that suicide prevention be recognized as a paramount concern on a global scale. There are many factors that have been identified as potential contributors to the occurrence and facilitation of suicide. These include but are not limited to inadequate social support, anxiety, feelings of loneliness, diminished self-perception and low self-esteem, challenges in managing anger, substance abuse, exposure to traumatic life events, and self-stigmatization in relation to mental health issues. Childhood traumas, including physical abuse, neglect, and emotional abuse, as well as the presence of lethal illnesses and mental problems, serve as illustrative instances of adverse experiences during early development.

Several underlying factors may be contributing to the occurrence of suicidal thoughts and behaviors. Inadequate coping mechanisms and a restricted ability to effectively address challenges significantly contribute to the propensity for and occurrence of

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suicidal inclinations and behaviors. Numerous factors might potentially impact an individual's inclination towards engaging in suicidal behavior. These factors include impulsivity, feelings of confinement, exposure to the suicide of another individual, and the availability of fatal methods.

Prior to an individual engaging in self-harm, several signs may manifest, suggesting the presence of underlying issues. It is important to engage in the reading and comprehension of these symptoms, while maintaining a state of vigilance and awareness about these indicators, with the aim of mitigating the prevalence of suicides. A diverse range of therapy interventions exists to facilitate the recovery of those experiencing suicidal ideation and engaging in self-harming behaviors. It is essential to exert oneself in the pursuit of seeking aid and support from others.

Conversely, there are several gaps and problems that must be addressed in order to provide assistance to these patients. Further investigation is required in order to fully understand the intricacies and complexities of spiritual practices that are intertwined and perplexing, with the ultimate goal of preventing individuals from engaging in self-destructive behaviors.

The essay highlights major concepts such as suicidal behavior, suicide attempts, cognitive interventions, etiology of suicide, and indicators of suicidal ideation.

Keywords: *Suicide, Reasons of Suicide, Results of Suicide, Rates of Suicide, Solving of Suicide Problem*

Introduction

In this section, we will provide some initial comments to set the context for our discussion.

The term "suicide attempt" is used to describe a situation in which an individual intends to engage in actions that might result in their own death. In actuality, he is experiencing profound desolation and a lack of agency, resulting in acute psychological anguish.

Based on statistical data, it is observed that around one million persons annually engage in suicidal behavior, resulting in self-inflicted death, while almost twenty million individuals have inclinations towards suicide. Consequently, this subject necessitates significant consideration. There may also exist instances of collective animal self-destruction via mass suicide. Numerous

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factors, including an individual's physiology and psychology, personal or family history, cognitive characteristics, exposure to stressful situations, and sociocultural context, might potentially contribute to the acceleration or predisposition towards suicidal behavior. The act of suicide is a complex phenomenon that is intertwined with a range of elements that contribute to its occurrence and preparation.

Methodology

A considerable proportion of individuals who confront the notion of terminating their lives by suicide exhibit a reluctance to seek professional intervention or engage in therapeutic measures. Furthermore, they often refrain from articulating the underlying motivations behind their contemplation of self-inflicted harm. Psychologists, psychiatrists, and other mental health professionals bear the burden of suicide prevention by their comprehension of the contextual factors influencing suicidal behaviors, their capacity to forecast the likelihood of such actions, and their development of innovative strategies. The comprehension of the contextual underpinnings of suicidal behaviors facilitates the achievement of this objective. The existing body of research offers insights into the hypotheses, risk factors, protective factors, and psychiatric treatments associated with the subject under investigation. In the majority of instances, the behavior may be attributed to the intricate interplay of several unique components.

The determinants and contributions

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Literature Review

Merely possessing suicidal ideation or harboring the intention to engage in self-inflicted harm does not meet the criteria to be classified as a suicide attempt. Nevertheless, the risk is heightened for the person when they possess the capability to execute the behaviors that align with their thoughts and goals. Situations characterized by embarrassment, tension, and final lack of achievement might potentially act as catalysts, prompting and expediting one's exertion. Several variables contribute to the facilitation of suicide attempts, including access to lethal weapons, impulsive behavior, feelings of confinement, and exposure to the suicide of another individual.

Insufficient social support, anxiety, feelings of loneliness, a diminished sense of self and low self-esteem, challenges with anger regulation, substance abuse, experiences of traumatic life events, and self-stigmatization are among the supplementary factors that influence suicidal tendencies. Another factor to consider is the presence of poor mental health.

Issues related to an individual's family are among the most influential underlying factors that impact a person. Coping with the experience of rejection or abandonment from a primary caregiver, such as a mother, father, or other key individual, may provide considerable challenges, particularly for children. The presence of inadequate familial communication, feelings of isolation stemming from life's obstacles, and experiences of concern and uncertainty may contribute to the manifestation of suicidal ideation and behaviors in children.

The adolescent may contemplate suicidal ideation due to the presence of neglectful and hostile parents, as well as a fragmented familial structure that fails to fulfill the child's needs. Another prevalent element that leads to suicidal ideation and behavior is the perception of being a source of hardship on one or several family members. The responsibility for providing care for oneself, particularly in cases of disability or severe illness, is with the person.

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Individuals may often engage in contemplation about suicide. Long-term fatal diseases may also have a profound influence on an individual, perhaps causing them to contemplate an earlier termination of their life.

The experience of profound distress and contemplation of self-harm may also be triggered by the bereavement of a beloved family member or the termination of an intimate interpersonal connection. It is conceivable that he may possess negative sentiments towards a former romantic partner who terminated their relationship. Occasionally, individuals are confronted with formidable hurdles that are arduous to overcome, such as being involved in gang-related or violent behavior. There is a potential for the person to be experiencing symptoms of depression and seeing self-inflicted harm as a means of seeking redemption for their errors. Exposure to suicide and the possibility to witness such an event are significant factors that may contribute to the development of suicidal ideation and behaviors. There exists a potentiality for him to establish a sense of identification with the aforementioned person. Individuals experiencing challenges related to their sexual orientation may encounter significant psychological distress, perhaps leading to the development of suicidal ideation.

The dissemination of news on individuals who have engaged in suicidal behavior, via various mediums such as written publications, visual media, and social networking platforms, is a significant element of consideration. Individuals with a proclivity towards self-harm may have intrusive suicidal ideation when exposed to explicit depictions of suicide, particularly when such portrayals include graphic details and visual elements that intensify the dramatic nature of the act.

Depression, anxiety, agitation, rumination, and anhedonia are psychological variables that have been identified as potential risk factors for engaging in suicidal behaviors. Another set of risk factors includes inflexible thinking and a lack of adaptability. Inadequate coping mechanisms and a restricted ability to effectively address challenges significantly contribute to the propensity for and occurrence of suicidal inclinations and behaviors. Certain personality traits, such as elevated levels of neuroticism or introversion, have been shown to be associated with

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suicidal ideation and behaviors. In addition to being associated with suicidal ideation and behavior, social isolation, inadequate social support, and poverty are also identified as risk factors. The occurrence of a prior suicide attempt is the foremost determinant in forecasting a future suicide.

The misuse of alcoholic drinks, heroin, cocaine, and methamphetamine has been consistently associated with a heightened propensity for engaging in suicidal behaviors. Another noteworthy finding emerged when researchers uncovered a correlation between those who exhibit a proclivity for smoking and those who have a proclivity for engaging in suicidal behaviors. The act of smoking has a double influence on persons' lives. Firstly, it directly contributes to the development of health complications that might ultimately result in self-inflicted mortality. Secondly, it induces changes in the brain's chemical composition, therefore fostering the emergence of suicidal thoughts and actions. In the year 2023, a significant event occurred, known as the Yldrmer incident.

Mental health issues, such as schizophrenia, borderline personality disorder, and bipolar disorder, have been shown to be significant indicators of suicidal ideation and behavior. Both post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and experiences of racism are often identified as significant contributors to the inclination towards suicide. Individuals who have challenges not just pertaining to their dietary habits, but also with regards to their psychological well-being, face a significant level of risk. In addition to psychoanalysis,

Findings

Recent research findings indicate that the use of pharmacological treatment has the potential to effectively decrease the incidence of suicide among individuals.

The occurrence of suicide may be attributed to traumatic childhood events, with a special emphasis on instances of sexual abuse. The correlation between experiencing sexual abuse and engaging in suicidal behavior is well established, with research indicating a higher likelihood

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of suicide among young males compared to young females. Intimate partner violence and childhood abuse are identified as supplementary risk factors contributing to the occurrence of suicide.

It is well recognized that several conditions, such as a demanding daily routine, unemployment or housing instability, financial challenges, the risk of bankruptcy, unemployment, and academic underachievement, might potentially serve as catalysts for suicide behaviors. Insufficient leisure and social skills, diminished self-esteem, and a dearth of optimism have all been identified as contributing characteristics associated with suicide thoughts, playing a significant part in its facilitation.

Argument

I have made the decision to end my own life. Residing in a socioeconomically deprived community and exhibiting a tendency to remain indoors significantly heighten an individual's susceptibility to engaging in self-harm. The facilitation of suicide behaviors includes cognitive processes such as catastrophizing, impulsivity, and maladaptive coping strategies. Certain occupations, such as law enforcement officers, firefighters, social workers, psychologists, psychiatrists, nurses, and other mental health professionals, are often exposed to instances of suicide, which may have a significant impact on their personal and professional lives. The aforementioned professions include individuals such as law enforcement officers, firefighters, social service specialists, psychologists, psychiatrists, nurses, and several other practitioners within the field of mental health.

Based on the present body of research, there exists a proposition suggesting a correlation between psychophysiological processes and suicidal inclinations. Indeed, it is worth noting that the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis assumes a substantial role in the behavioral patterns associated with suicide. There is a prevailing belief that deviant levels of cortisol, together with

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an inaccurate cortisol reaction to stress, play a role in the manifestation of suicidal inclinations. The presence of latent DNA components under the surface has the potential to influence suicidal ideation and behavior, especially in cases where there are familial instances of suicide that serve as triggering factors. Nevertheless, it is important to acknowledge that environmental factors that are linked to epigenetics have a substantial impact.

Various theories have been proposed to explain the complex phenomenon of suicide.

Freud is the seminal figure to whom we must direct our attention in order to elucidate the roots of the perspectives around suicide. Freud's psychoanalytic theory posits that sorrow may be seen as a manifestation of internalized animosity. The author posits that the absence of a primary caregiver, along with feelings of guilt, longing, and anger, serves as a catalyst for individuals to redirect these emotions inwards. Consequently, they endeavor to inflict punishment onto themselves via the act of suicide. In the context of Freudian theory, the year 2019 may be examined and analyzed.

In contrast, Melanie Klein posits the existence of supplementary impulses, which include not only the mirroring of internal aggression, but also the inner targeting and subsequent defense of the disagreeable object. Klein and Freud were particularly interested in elucidating the underlying reasons behind the self-inflicted deaths of those experiencing profound sadness. Individuals with narcissistic traits may possess alternative motivations, especially in the event of experiencing a decline in their social standing, a diminished perception of their own value, or an impaired capacity to regulate their emotional states. The individuals experience feelings of embarrassment and remorse in response to these experiences.

Experiencing a sense of inadequacy or self-doubt. For those who hold this perspective, ending their own life may be seen as the ultimate form of retaliation. According to Klein (2002),

Lacan, a renowned French psychoanalyst, and psychiatrist postulated the existence of two discrete categories of suicidal inclinations that need examination: enactment and execution.

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Individuals who engage in suicide behavior first have a persistent conviction that they are perceptible to others, both visually and audibly. The individual in question

One may contemplate the potential for a transformation in indifference. The individuals in question have not entirely lost their optimism and possess a strong aspiration to achieve their goals.

Maintained at a certain degree of security. Conversely, the second group has a deliberate inclination towards self-termination. According to Homer (2013), it was referenced.

Wenzel and Beck (Yildirim, 2023, p. 29) have presented a concise overview of a cognitive model as an alternative evaluation framework. Based on this particular perspective, the peril of suicide exacts a significant toll on an individual's well-being.

The phenomenon under consideration arises from the intricate interaction between cognitive processes, schemas, and preexisting conceptions pertaining to evaluations. The inclusion of the diathesis stress model is vital in these explanations, since it encompasses three essential components: cognitive processes pertaining to vulnerability factors, cognitive processes related to psychiatric disorders, and cognitive processes associated with suicidal behavior. The individual known as Joiner tragically took their own life.

Based on this proposition, the experience of despair and the manifestation of suicidal ideation and behavior may be attributed to a decline in one's feeling of affiliation, coupled with a perceived escalation in onerous obligations. According to Yildirim (2023),

Indicators of Suicidal Behavior

Both premeditated and impulsive instances of suicide are equally viable. The capacity to identify these indicators is of utmost importance as they might serve as an appeal for aid prior

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to an individual engaging in a purposeful act of self-harm. There is a potential for these persons to experience increased isolation from their environment, as well as alterations in their patterns of eating and sleeping. Individuals may experience emotions of diminished self-value and exhibit indications of despondency as a consequence. Individuals may often exhibit tearfulness, have difficulties in maintaining concentration, and endure intense physical suffering. During the course of the conversation, the topic of suicide may be broached. Their field of vision becomes sufficiently blocked, so impeding their ability to see other pathways for issue resolution.

In addition, individuals may expeditiously alter their social group should they become disinterested in engaging in sexual activities. There is a potential for individuals to express dissatisfaction and a sense of powerlessness and despair. Individuals may articulate feelings of irritation with their perceived lack of affection, desirability, and caring from others. There is a potential for a decrease in their behavioral tendencies or an increase in their inclination towards hostility. They begin to develop an interest in songs that explore the topic of suicide and its subsequent consequences. Now, individuals may start the process of drafting their ultimate wills and testaments. There exists a potential for individuals to engage in the act of discarding their belongings or distributing them to others.

Strategies for both mitigating and preventing instances of suicide

Individuals displaying suicidal behaviors and thoughts need the provision of social support services. The period during which

During this period, several activities emerged that offered a pleasant break from the monotonous nature of their daily lives, including

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Engaging in recreational pursuits such as hiking and fishing might potentially provide significant benefits. It is essential to provide medical intervention for individuals' physical problems and address their mental disorders in order to mitigate the occurrence of suicidal ideation. Individuals must seek therapy if they are suffering the adverse consequences of drug usage. Individuals diagnosed with medical diseases such as hypothyroidism, Alzheimer's disease, brain tumors, or lupus, who are prescribed drugs such as beta blockers and steroids, require vigilant monitoring owing to the potential manifestation of emotional symptoms and difficulties. There is a potential correlation between the use of antidepressants, especially when recommended to senior individuals, and their potential efficacy in mitigating suicidal behaviors. Individuals who experience severe depression or bipolar disorder are often administered lithium as a therapeutic intervention. Individuals who have been clinically diagnosed with schizophrenia often use the medication Klozapin with the intention of reducing the occurrence of suicidal ideation. Research findings have shown that the use of ketamine, a dissociative anesthetic, has the potential to mitigate suicidal thoughts.

Individuals who possess an optimistic outlook and have strong religious or spiritual convictions are shown to get support and experience a reduction in suicide ideation.

It is essential to notify the family members of the person of the possibility of suicidal ideation, and it is recommended to actively urge their involvement in providing support and help. If these persons fail to make any effort to ask about obtaining aid, it is imperative that they be admitted to the hospital. Even during periods of sleep, it is important to maintain constant vigilance and refrain from leaving them unattended.

Electroconvulsive therapy (ECT), sometimes referred to as EKT, is an extensively used therapeutic modality for addressing suicidal thoughts. Cognitive treatments, including Dialectical Behavior Therapy (DBT), Cognitive Therapy-Suicide Preventive (CT-SP), and Brief Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (BCBT), are therapeutic modalities that have been identified as potentially effective in the prevention of suicidal ideation and behaviors.

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There is a need to expand and sustain crisis support centers, while considering the potential use of the Cooperative Assessment and Management of Suicide (CAMS) as a conceptual framework. The possibility to mitigate suicide risk exists within the realms of economic growth, poverty reduction, social help for the elderly, and enhanced social relationships.

The ultimate conclusion

The trajectory of human existence poses challenges for a sizable portion of the population; yet it is important to note that not all persons facing these difficulties will contemplate or participate in suicidal ideation or behavior. The global population comprises more than twenty million persons who have suicidal ideation and engage in suicidal behaviors. Annually, over 800,000 lives are lost worldwide as a result of suicide. A considerable proportion, namely 60%, of persons experiencing stress and facing challenges refrain from seeking any kind of support. Only a small number of individuals are accepted to treatment facilities that provide preventive interventions, pharmacological therapies, or psychological therapy.

Conclusion

Based on the existing body of research, it is evident that there is a pressing need to create a substantial repertoire of novel psychosocial interventions aimed at mitigating the prevalence of suicidal ideation among individuals.

The acts and efforts undertaken. Prior to seeking aid, it is vital to possess a comprehensive comprehension of the obstacles that will be encountered. The incorporation of contemporary psychological findings, advancements, and enhancements is necessary in order to achieve optimal efficacy in suicide prevention and intervention efforts. The encouragement of

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perseverance and the execution of projects are particularly critical for countries with low and middle income.

The analysis of the internet, social media, written media, and visual media and the potential need for regulation are of utmost importance.

In order to gain insight into the factors that contribute to suicidal ideation and behaviors, it is essential to actively seek guidance from a specialist, get a referral to a certified expert, and engage in therapy sessions. The acquisition of medicine may be beneficial in some circumstances. The efficacy and stability of the therapy are enhanced with the use of pharmaceutical intervention.

Limitations

This research is limited to the extent of the data in the world literature. The research is restricted to the research about the related subjects. It is limited to literature surveys.

Notices

Assessment: This study was assessed by internal and external advisors.

Conflicts of Interest: The author declared no conflicts of interest in relation to this article.

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Ethical Declaration

This study aims to ensure that scientific research is made in accordance with basic principles such as honesty, respect for the findings and creations of others and aims to realize these principles in the field of related disciplines.

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